

“Transported to a better place”: The influence of virtual reality on the behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia

Maria Matsangidou^{a,*}, Theodoros Solomou^b, Fotos Frangoudes^a, Ersi Papayianni^c,
Natalie Kkeli^c, Constantinos S. Pattichi^{a,b}

^a CYENS Centre of Excellence, Nicosia, Cyprus

^b Department of Computer Science, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus

^c Archangelos Michael Elderly People Nursing Home/Rehabilitation Centre for Patients with Alzheimer, Nicosia, Cyprus

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Virtual reality
Dementia
Patient-centered design
Psychophysiological responses
Behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia

ABSTRACT

Emerging research supports that institutionalisation may contribute to the development of the behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia. Many studies have documented that Virtual Reality can enhance symptom management in people diagnosed with dementia. We design a Virtual Reality system to improve the symptom management of people diagnosed with dementia residing in long-term care services. Twenty people with dementia were enrolled in the study to evaluate the developed solution. Following semi-structured interviews and observations, a thematic analysis was conducted to analyse the results of the system. Heart Rate and Eye-tracking data were recorded to enhance the reliability of the findings. Our findings indicate that Virtual Reality might be able to improve the quality of life of people diagnosed with dementia, as it is highly effective in reducing behavioral and psychological symptoms associated with dementia, including aggression, agitation, anxiety, apathy, and depression. Additionally, Virtual Reality was found to be a possible solution for pain management, reminiscence therapy, and dementia diagnosis.

1. Introduction

Dementia is an umbrella term for conditions leading to cognitive and social functioning deterioration. It affects the afflicted person's memory, thinking, orientation, comprehension, calculation, learning capacity, language, and judgment. Dementia is commonly accompanied by behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia (BPSD), which include challenging behaviours such as mood disturbances and lack of emotional control (World Health Organization (WHO), 2021). These symptoms significantly impact the quality of life (HRQoL) of both People with Dementia (PwD) and their caregivers (Appel et al., 2016; Kales et al., 2015; Sampson et al., 2014; White et al., 2017). The symptoms of BPSD can range from aggressive physical or verbal behaviour towards self and others (e.g., hitting, grabbing, picking/scratching their skin, making loud noises, shouting angrily, cursing, screaming), to restlessness, irritability, and agitated behaviours (e.g., pacing nervously, moving excessively), or even to depression, apathy, and diminished motivation (Alzheimer's Society of Canada, 2019; Pelletier and Landreville, 2007; Savva et al., 2009; World Health Organization (WHO),

2022).

In 2021, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that the total number of People with Dementia (PwD) around the world exceeds fifty-five million people, and more importantly, the number of PwD is expected to rise to one hundred thirty-nine million by 2050 (World Health Organization (WHO), 2021). As dementia is the seventh most common cause of death worldwide and the leading cause of disability and dependency for older people (World Health Organization (WHO), 2021), a Global Action Plan has been developed and released with a major priority to improve the Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL) for PwD (Verbeek et al., 2010; World Health Organization (WHO), 2017).

According to previous research, most interventions for PwD that aim to improve their HRQoL and decrease the BPSD are mostly based on overprescribed and ineffective neuroleptic or sedating medications and physical barriers (such as alarms and locks), which were found to accelerate the cognitive and physical decline of the PwD (Banerjee, 2009; Banerjee et al., 2011; Appel et al.; 2020). Specifically, the use of neuroleptic or sedating medication has been associated with the

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: m.matsangidou@cyens.org.cy (M. Matsangidou).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2024.103413>

Received 15 November 2023; Received in revised form 27 November 2024; Accepted 27 November 2024

Available online 30 November 2024

1071-5819/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

condition worsening (e.g., faster cognitive decline), cardiovascular disorders, infections, drowsiness, nausea, fatigue, weight gain, headaches, and increases in anxiety, distress, and aggressiveness (Banerjee et al., 2011; Appel et al., 2016; White et al., 2017). Thus, and in line with the Global Action Plan (World Health Organization (WHO), 2017), it was recommended that best practices reflect the use of pharmacological interventions and physical restraints only as a last resort to treat complex cases where non-pharmacological interventions have proven unsuccessful.

Non-pharmacological interventions, which include sensory stimulation (e.g., aromatherapy, thermal bath, calming music, hand massage), social engagement, exposure to interests and activities, alternative environments, and therapies based on behavior, reminiscence, music, and art, are now the preferred approach for treating BPSD. A growing body of evidence supports the effectiveness of these interventions. For instance, reminiscence therapy has been associated with reduced challenging behaviors (Kasl-Godley and Gatz, 2000), as well as improved cognition and mood (Woods et al., 2018). Similarly, participation in art and music therapies has been shown to decrease agitation, anxiety, and depression (Gómez-Romero et al., 2017; Kishita et al., 2020; Livingston et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2017). Overall, a special emphasis is placed on the patient-centric philosophy of care (Kitwood and Kitwood, 1997), and the implementation of individualised formulation-led interventions.

To date, computer technology, and especially Virtual Reality (VR), has provided significant opportunities to support and enhance non-pharmacological interventions due to its ability to immerse users in diverse environments and situations. VR is particularly valuable for PwD because it can transcend physical boundaries, offering the experience of being in an entirely different setting—such as a forest or a beach—while they are physically confined to a room. This capability is especially important for PwD, who often face isolation and environmental constraints due to limited mobility or the need for constant supervision. By simulating rich, calming, and familiar environments, VR can alleviate the sense of confinement and isolation that many PwD experience. Moreover, VR can stimulate emotional responses and trigger positive, responsive behaviors, which are often difficult to achieve in a controlled, physical environment. For example, exposure to soothing natural settings or exploring familiar landmarks can evoke and amplify responsive behaviors and emotional reactions. This immersive experience has the potential to provide therapeutic benefits without the need for physical movement or travel, which may be impossible for many PwD. In terms of feasibility, recent studies have shown promising results in using VR with PwD. Research suggests that PwD respond positively to VR environments, finding the experience enjoyable and stimulating. These results highlight VR's potential as a powerful tool to engage patients, reduce feelings of isolation, and enhance cognitive and emotional stimulation, making it an innovative, non-invasive solution for improving the quality of life for this population (D'Cunha et al., 2019; Rose et al., 2018).

The goal, therefore, remains to deliver non-pharmacological innovations enhanced by the development of proper information systems for dementia, which can support HRQoL. This paper presents a VR non-pharmacological intervention for PwD designed to improve the HRQoL and the emotional well-being of the demented person, including any associated BPSD.

1.1. VR interventions to improve the HRQoL and reduce BPSD

Non-pharmacological approaches, such as digital therapeutics (DTx), provide emerging, technology-driven methods for delivering personalized care. DTx enables remote delivery, scalability, and online monitoring, enhancing individualized care's effectiveness (Garg and Saluja, 2023; Dang et al., 2020; Schneider et al., 2024). With the global DTx market projected to reach approximately 10.09 billion USD by 2029, there is increasing emphasis on mental and behavioral health management, highlighting the growing significance of these interventions in the healthcare sector (Statista, 2024; Fortune Business, 2024). Among the

technology-based non-pharmaceutical interventions for dementia, chatbots and cognitive games are widely used to enhance patient engagement and provide therapeutic support. For example, AI-driven chatbots like Replika, 2024 offer personalized conversational interactions that help alleviate loneliness and stimulate cognitive engagement (Ta et al., 2020). Similarly, games like Sea Hero Quest are designed to test and support spatial navigation, a critical cognitive skill often impaired in dementia (Alzheimer's Research, 2024). Other projects, like Lumosity, use gamified exercises to improve cognitive functions and mood (McCallum and Boletsis, 2013; Hardy and Scanlon, 2009). These tools promote cognitive health and mood improvement and offer scalable, patient-centered care alternatives accessible to users worldwide, making them an essential part of modern dementia care strategies.

In recent years, VR has become one of the most accessible and low-cost solutions in the healthcare domain and it has been used in a variety of medical applications, including but not limited, to areas of delivering treatment to people with mental health disorders (e.g., anxiety and depression (Fodor et al., 2018; Zeng et al., 2018), eating disorders (Clus et al., 2018; Matsangidou et al., 2022), phobias (Botella et al., 2017; Parsons and Rizzo, 2008), psychosis (Rus-Calafell et al., 2018), paranoid ideations (Valmaggia et al., 2007), schizophrenia (Park et al., 2011)).

Current research suggests that VR can be a reliable, feasible, and acceptable solution, promoting engagement and providing an enjoyable experience for PwD (Rose et al., 2018; Appel et al., 2021), since it offers the user multisensory interactions and feedback (e.g., visual, auditory, tactile, and/or olfactory). Within the context of the Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) research field, the elements a VR system should incorporate for PwD have been examined, with the main conclusion that special effort should be placed on creating personalised experiences that take into consideration the preferences and skill level of each user (Hodge et al., 2018; Matsangidou et al., 2022; Siriaraya and Ang, 2014; Tabbaa et al., 2019). More generally, most of the research on VR for PwD has focused on the improvement of the capabilities that deteriorate over time due to the progression of the disease. These capabilities typically relate to cognition (Sayma et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2021), memory (Optale et al., 2010), spatial navigation (Cushman et al., 2008; Zakzanis et al., 2009), executive functions such as planning activities (Manera et al., 2015) and attention (Doniger et al., 2018; Manera et al., 2016), and motor control (Matsangidou et al., 2022; 2022; 2020).

To date, recent studies have reported successful deployments of VR for PwD. However, further evaluation is still needed due to inconclusive results at this early stage (Appel et al., 2016; Huang and Yang, 2022; Saredakis et al., 2021; 2020; Walden and Feliciano, 2022). Our study explores the potential benefits of VR for PwD with BPSD. Our goal is to create virtually enhanced experiences for PwD living in locked hospital units for care. Our approach is to use PwD reflections to draw implications and recommendations for delivering human-centric experiences. This will ultimately improve the HRQoL of PwD residing in long-term care, enabling them to engage with the world beyond physical restrictions in a mindful, joyful, and sustainable way. In this paper, we begin by mapping the important aspects of the relationship between PwD and VR interactions. We then correlate PwD's subjective claims with physiological responses (Heart Rate and eye-tracking). By doing so, we identify key design principles that can improve the VR experience for PwD. Having the above in mind, we propose the following research questions:

RQ1: What therapeutic benefits does VR provide in managing BPSD and improving the overall HRQoL for PwD?

RQ2: How can VR systems be designed to incorporate personalization, social interaction, and accessibility to enhance acceptance and effectiveness in dementia care?

RQ3: What insights do physiological responses, such as heart rate and eye-tracking data, offer about the emotional and behavioral impacts of VR interventions on PwD?

RQ4: How can VR applications in dementia care address diagnostic challenges, mitigate loneliness, and facilitate reminiscence therapy through innovative and immersive experiences?

2. Methods

2.1. Ethics

People diagnosed with dementia were recruited from a National Health Alzheimer’s and Dementia’s Disease hospital. This study was approved by the National Bioethics Committee (the reference is hidden for blind review). A consent form was signed by all participants before the study.

2.2. Participants

Twenty people with mild to severe dementia, participated in this study. The diagnosis was confirmed using the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) (Anthony et al., 1982), ranging between 3 and 24. Table 1 displays detailed demographic information. Participants had no prior experience using VR. All participants had a normal or corrected vision and no history of severe motion sickness.

2.3. Materials

- Heart rate (HR). Research has shown that HR provides a valid and reliable measure of emotional arousal (Anttonen and Surakka, 2005). Therefore, we measure the participant’s HR every second to identify emotional arousal to the visual elements.
- Eye-tracking data (EYE). The technology allowed the analysis of the behaviour of PwD, thus providing the opportunity to gain a better understanding of what they were looking and experiencing.
- Observations were recorded during the sessions by two researchers to identify and record the interaction between the people diagnosed with dementia and the VR system, as well as the presence or absence of BPSD traits and physical interactions between the PwD and the VR system.
- Semi-structured interviews were conducted by two researchers. We examined the ‘technology acceptance’ of VR using semi-structured interview questions related to the usability, practicality, and immersiveness of the system. For example, people diagnosed with dementia were asked whether they felt immersed in the experience; whether they forgot about the physical boundaries of the room; as well as whether the VR headset was comfortable to wear. Questions were also asked regarding the emotional effects of VR and related to observations made during the VR exposure.

Table 1
Participants demographics.

Demographics	Value	N	M	SD
Sex	Male	7		
	Female	13		
Mean Age		73.15	16.17	
MMSE	Mild	6	22.17	1.52
	Moderate	8	15.25	1.67
	Severe	6	7.83	3.82
	Total		15.10	6.16
Primary Diagnosis	Dementia	20		
Secondary Diagnoses	Major depressive disorder	6		
	Anxiety disorders	6		
Additional Diagnoses	Bipolar disorder	2		
	Epileptic seizures	2		
	Psychosis	2		
	Schizophrenia	1		
	Delusional disorder	1		

2.4. Study design and procedure

The study was conducted in a hospital setting, in a room familiar to PwD. Initially, a researcher with a background in psychology and human-computer interaction (HCI), as well as experience in working with PwD, explained the study procedures to the PwD and ensured they were comfortable with the equipment and familiarized with the process. This was particularly important as PwD may have challenging behaviors, and introducing a new modality to this patient group requires some time for familiarization. Subsequently, the PwD were escorted by the researcher and offered an A3 paper “Menu” of the available Virtual Environments (see Fig. 2 for a selection of environments). The HCI researcher, possessing a background in psychology, verbally described each environment while simultaneously indicating the corresponding images. In instances where the PwD did not promptly choose a specific environment, the researcher initiated a second descriptive cycle, employing alternative and simpler language to enhance understanding. In cases where PwD were struggling to engage and select an environment, this process continued until they showed an interest in an environment. Each PwD could select up to three virtual environments from a list of 10 available options.

To prevent adverse effects such as dizziness associated with using the system, a maximum duration of 15 min was recommended for visiting the environments. Transitions between environments occurred at the participant’s request; however, if necessary, the researcher would notify the PwD when the allocated time (i.e., 5 min per environment) in a particular environment had ended and ask whether they wished to stay longer or proceed to the next environment. Despite the recommended time limit of 15 min, some participants were so deeply engaged in the experience that they expressed reluctance to remove their headsets once the allotted exposure time had ended. This phenomenon was particularly notable among patients suffering from depression, as the VR experience frequently elicited feelings of pleasure (refer to Sections 3.1.1.1 and 3.1.3.1). In such instances, participants were granted the opportunity to extend their engagement by an additional five minutes. The researcher offered prompts to facilitate the process of concluding the experience.

A software engineer researcher was also present to manage the equipment throughout the VR session. Both researchers kept observational notes during the VR session and monitored the eye tracking and HR activity to proactively react. Then a semi-structured interview with the PwD where both researchers were once again present to make sure that insights from psychology, HCI, and technical perspectives were recorded. Each session lasted approximately 40 min.

2.5. Apparatus

The system design built upon a systematic review that explored the feasibility of using VR for people with neurological disorders and dementia (Schiza et al., 2019). The entire design process has been documented and published for transparency (Matsangidou et al., 2022). We first identified the requirements for the VR system, using reflections from 51 healthcare professionals (HCPs) and 24 PwD and created an initial prototype. We then assessed the system’s usability and sense of presence with 16 HCPs, who used the system as both users and administrators. Based on the feedback from the HCPs, we refined the system and conducted a pilot study with 20 older adults suffering from Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) to guide the system’s design (Matsangidou et al., 2023). After refining the system again based on the feedback from the MCI older adults, we evaluated it once more with the 16 HCPs. Finally, we evaluated, using quantitative measures, the usability and effectiveness of the system with PwD (Matsangidou et al., 2023). In this study, we present a thorough evaluation of the final product with PwD.

Fig. 1. The depicted visualisation showcases an individual with dementia who is experiencing a virtual environment and reminiscing about a memory of a car accident that resulted in them being bound to a wheelchair for life. Notably, the graph indicates a significant increase in heart rate when the individual is looking at the car racing, which is followed by a sudden decline upon shifting their attention back to the sea.

Fig. 2. The display portrays some of the virtual environments given at the PwD and some of our participants (PwD) during the VR exposure.

The VR system for the study was developed by the authors using the Unity¹ game engine. The 3D models for the virtual environments were retrieved from the Unity Asset Store and repurposed to run on a VIVE Pro Eye VR system². While a PwD was wearing the VR headset, the displayed content was mirrored on a laptop screen in real-time. The PwD’s gaze was tracked through the HMD’s embedded eye tracker and visualized on the laptop screen using a ray. The visualized ray was based on the head position and orientation, and the direction of the PwD’s gaze, and reflected where they were looking at within the environment. Through the same ray, the exact object they were looking at was also identified by detecting its overlap with pre-defined points of interest within the environment. Finally, a Samsung Galaxy Active 2³ smartwatch was worn by the participants to track their HR. For this purpose, a smartwatch-based app was used called HeartRateOBS, which streamed via Bluetooth the HR data every second. The data were then received by a Desktop application, developed using Python, that stored the data locally on the phone.

3. Findings and discussion

When assessing the potential of VR for PwD, it is essential to understand the unique aspects, advantages, and limitations VR has to offer. For this purpose, we conducted a thematic analysis, which involves identifying, interpreting, and reporting patterns within datasets (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The findings from interviews and observations in the study emphasize these key aspects. The outcomes are also reinforced and explained through the quantitative data recorded in the study (i.e., the HR and eye tracking data). The interviews and the observation notes were coded by two researchers. The two researchers identified patterns in the data, which were then coded and refined into themes. To further refine and verify the themes, the researchers discussed them with medical experts and caregivers who were quietly present throughout the data collection process to intervene and assist the PwD if necessary. The thematic analysis revealed three core themes and nine subthemes. The three core themes that emerged from the data were: “Therapeutic benefits”, “Blending the real with the un-real”, and “Material properties and interactivity”.

Table 2 presents the summary of the thematic analysis. For the presentation of the data, we used the following coding: PwD = person with dementia, R = Researcher, source: observation notes or interview transcript.

¹ www.unity.com.

² www.vive.com/eu/product/vive-pro-eye.

³ <https://www.samsung.com/global/galaxy/galaxy-watch-active2/#galaxy-watch-active2>.

Table 2
Thematic scheme summary for people diagnosed with dementia.

Therapeutic benefits	Blending the real with the unreal	Material properties and interactivity
Affective responses and reduced BPSD	Stuck in a loop	Feasibility and acceptability of technology
Pain alleviation	Transitioning between the two worlds	Material properties
Reminiscence therapy	The role of caregivers in the multiverse	Augmentation of self: neural impulses and interactions

3.1. Therapeutic benefits

During the study, we observed various therapeutic benefits for the PwD. Here, we present three sub-themes arising from our analysis: (a) Affective responses and reduced BPSD; (b) Pain alleviation; and (c) Reminiscence therapy, which overly improved the HRQoL of the PwD.

3.1.1. Affective responses and reduced BPSD

Based on the collected data, 14/20 PwD presented severe BPSD, with either aggressive, anxious and/or depressive responses. Apathy and lack of motivation were diagnosed at higher levels, accounting for 17/20 PwD. People who have been diagnosed with dementia and have a history of BPSD have a high likelihood, up to 75 %, of exhibiting aggressive and disruptive behaviour (Sampson et al., 2014; White et al., 2017). Such behaviours in PwD are defined as intentional, overt, harmful acts toward another person, object, or oneself (Sultana et al., 2020). Six PwD presented verbal and physical aggression toward themselves before the VR exposure. Caregivers reported that one PwD also exhibited aggressive behaviour towards other PwD and caregivers, though this was not observed in our presence.

Based on our research, it appears that VR can help alleviate BPSD in individuals with dementia. Specifically, we observed a decrease in aggression and agitation during and after the VR session, which was corroborated by the reduced HR of the individuals and previous studies that also reported a reduction in agitation and HR after exposure to virtual nature (Reynolds et al., 2018). Contrary to the pre-exposure data and in line with recent pilot studies (Appel et al., 2016; Walden and Feliciano, 2022; Sultana et al., 2021), all of the PwD displayed a reduction in aggressive or agitated behaviours during the VR session. It is worth mentioning that the decrease in aggressive or agitated behaviours persisted after the end of the session. It is even more interesting that the caregivers, who observed the PwD after they returned to the usual care validated the persistence of the reduced aggressive behaviours for a couple of hours after the VR exposure.

Fig. 3 schematically illustrates the changes in HR over time as the PwD is exposed to three different virtual environments. The HR data indicated that the longer the PwD was immersed in a VR environment,

the lower their HR responses were. A noticeable change in HR was observed during the transition between the three virtual environments. In particular, during the transition between the three virtual environments, the PwD’s HR increased, and anxious behaviours were observed. Similarly, it was observed that the longer the PwD was immersed in a VR environment, the less agitation and aggression they displayed.

Before VR exposure, the researcher explains the experiment to the PwD:

“PwD: [The PwD looks at R very angrily.] Do whatever you want. I don’t care; I am leaving this place [referring to the nursing home], I am here only for a while, and I will soon go home.

R: Do you miss your home?

PwD: [She raises her voice and angrily points at the researcher]. Listen to me! You! Listen to me; I am leaving my daughter will come to take me home.”

After VR exposure:

“R: How do you feel?

PwD: [The PwD looks at R calmly with a smile] I am happy.

R: And what makes you happy?

PwD: [The PwD looks at R with eyes wide open and seems impressed. Then the PwD uses plural language, implying that R, who was present in the physical room during the virtual reality exposure, was also present in the virtual environment] We saw so many nice things, we saw the birds, the grass, the sky; we saw the trees, the flowers, beautiful flowers, and the breeze, oh that breeze which made the flowers to move... I will keep everything in here! [PwD points toward their head]” [PwD2, Interview]

Based on previous research, a possible cause of agitation and aggression in PwD is the sense of loneliness and the monotony of everyday living (Lyketsos et al., 2011). Based on our findings PwD who reside in long-term care are constantly experiencing loneliness and monotony (Lyketsos et al., 2011; Shen et al., 2022; Wood et al., 2009). Many people diagnosed with dementia have expressed a desire to have their families around, as they have been missing them greatly. Additionally, a majority of these people diagnosed with dementia have reported feeling bored and fatigued due to the repetitive nature of their daily routine.

During VR exposure - Once the PwD wears the VR shouts:

“PwD: Thank you! You have given me back my life - it’s a miracle! You’ve brought God back into my life.” [PwD7, Observation]

After VR exposure:

Fig. 3. The graph depicts a significant drop in HR during VR exposure in three distinct virtual environments (indicated by white backgrounds), followed by a sharp increase during the transition phase (indicated by orange backgrounds).

R: What made you so happy?

PwD: [The PwD look at R with gratitude] Thank you! Thank you! Thank you! I wish you all the happiness in the world for the good you have done for me. I can give you my soul if you wish, just promise that you won't take this away from me.

R: What is it that you don't want to lose?

PwD: The Lord! My life! My eyes! Don't cut down all the flowers. Don't lock me back in here!

R: Don't you like being here?

PwD: I do, but... I miss life. Every day is the same here. Always the same! [The PwD seems sad]

R: But you do so many activities, don't you? There is a music session, and art, and sports classes...

PwD: Yes, but there is no God! No flowers. No birds. No animals. No... No... [PwD tries to find the word "river" she moves her fingers like waves]

R: Water?

PwD: Water! [PwD giggles and smiles].” [PwD7, Interview]

Another factor contributing to agitation and aggression in PwD is their physical environment and lack of privacy. Previous research recognized that being locked into a hospital environment can negatively affect the levels of aggression the PwD are experiencing. To reduce agitated behaviours, among others, spacious rooms, out-reach experiences enhanced by nature, and low-stimulus environments have been suggested (Canatsey and Roper, 1997; Chou et al., 2002; Waller and Masterson, 2015). In line with a recent study (Tabbaa et al., 2019), our findings suggest that VR could be used to create an isolated, private space for the PwD. In particular, our findings support the reduction of aggregated behaviours during and after VR exposure. Our research emphasizes the significance of experiencing pleasant environments in private settings and confirms the findings of a previous study (Tabbaa et al., 2019), while it also addresses the limitations of previous research, which lacked data on aggressive behaviours and had a small sample size of only 8 PwD (Tabbaa et al., 2019).

Before VR exposure the PwD speaks and acts angrily, making loud noises and picking his hands. He chooses to be exposed to the VR bedroom environment, where he sits quietly for a couple of minutes.

During the VR session, he starts to smile and sing:

“PwD: aa.. olt... uuu... I am alone in life but the old radio on the table [He looks at an old virtual radio] playing music, reminding me of the days to come, reminding me that life is beautiful [He started to move his feet as if he was dancing while being seated], reminding me that I will smile again [He smiles], do not worry, don't be sorry, don't be sorry... [As he keeps singing, the lyrics convey a similar message as stated above].

R: Our session is about to be over; shall we remove the glasses?

PwD: No. [With a tone of sadness].

R: Okay, you can stay a bit longer, but then we need to take off the glasses, alright?

PwD: [Remains in silence for a while and then starts to sing again] The old radio...

R: Our session is over; shall we remove the glasses?

PwD: No.

R: Would it be alright if we waited two more minutes before removing them?

PwD: Hmm ok.” [PwD15, Observations]

After VR:

R: How are you feeling? Did you enjoy it?

PwD: Oh yes. Can we do it again?

R: Maybe another day. What exactly did you like?

PwD: The silence! No one was talking to me, and no one was screaming around me. I was alone. I was in peace, so quiet. Can we do it again?

R: Will do. Another day. This is a promise.

PwD: Hmm. I will leave now, but you did make a promise. [He points at R and smiles before leaving the room with the nursing staff]” [PwD15, Interview]

Even though all PwD enjoyed being exposed to the VR and their BPSD symptoms were reduced during and after the VR exposure, it is worth mentioning that as for depressive reactions, an interesting observation was made. During the VR exposure, all PwD reacted pleasurably, and it was documented that their feelings of sadness was reduced. However, some of the PwD reported feeling melancholic once the VR session ended. A couple of them asked when they will be able to use the system again.

“PwD: What you did for me today gave me courage. Thank you.

R: Courage?

PwD: Living here is exhausting. Don't get me wrong, all the staff and the admin are doing their best, without them I am not able to survive; but still, I am not able to walk, I must wait for them to shower me, or to take me to the yard. Here it was quiet, I enjoyed being alone, next to the beach, looking around. Now, that I am not wearing the glasses, I feel so sad [He starts to cry and then anxiously continues in tears] Please come again, will you come again?” [PwD18, Interview]

“PwD: I have a question for you. Can I ask you a question?

R: Sure!

PwD: Why are you doing this?

R: Our goal is to help you feel nice.

PwD: Oh, I felt wonderful, not just nice, but what's in it for you?

R: If you felt good then that is my gain.

PwD: [PwD got upset and start to yell at R] NO! NO! NO! That can't be it. I felt so good, but if you are not getting something out of it then why should you come again? And I need you to come again, I need this, do you understand, I need this, so tell me what you want from me so that I can give it to you so that I know you will come back [PwD looks sad, almost ready to cry].” [PwD20, Interview]

Apathy is associated with poor HRQoL for PwD residing in long-term care and it is one of the most frequently underrecognized and overlooked neurological disorder symptoms (Selbæk et al., 2013; Zuidema et al., 2007; Ballard et al., 2001). Similarly, in our study, apathy was one of the core diagnoses for our participants. As one can easily observe apathy demonstrated the greatest cognitive improvement during and after VR exposure. Almost all PwD entered the room highly apathetic and unmotivated but once they were exposed to the VR environment they turn to be happily alerted.

Before VR exposure the PwD looks dull and apathetic. He has a limited interest in things, and he is not even responding to R. PwD does not keep eye contact with R or any elements in the physical space.

“R: Where are we now?

PwD: [Looking at the floor, saying nothing and moving his shoulders up and down]

R: We are in a room. Aren't we?

PwD: [Looking at the floor, saying nothing]

R: [R asks the PwD multiple times and in different ways the same question until the PwD shows some form of agreement]

PwD: mmm [shows agreement]

R: Mr X. Would you like to visit a forest?

PwD: [Looking at the floor, saying nothing]

R: A river?

PwD: [Looking at the floor, saying nothing]

R: [R asks the PwD of several virtual environments until the PwD shows some form of interest] What about some cows?

PwD: [Looked at R]

R: Ohhh! So cows? Do you like cows?

PwD: I... I... used to have.

R: So cows it is! [PwD19, Observations]

During VR exposure (see Fig. 4 for the appropriate setting):

“PwD: oh! Look-look! [He points with his finger – he moves his finger] Where is my finger I can’t see it?

R: I can. It is ok, look at the cows!

PwD: ohhhh! There is one and two, and oh look at the goats, and hahaha [laughs happily] there is a donkey! A donkey! He whistles at the donkey and then he shouts “Hey you with the big ears” hahaha. So, listen to me, do you see the cows? [points with his finger]

R: Of course, I do.

PwD: This kind of cows are the cows for producing milk not for digging the fields, and the donkey is for carrying the harvest, and the flowers, the flowers are pink and white, and they are called, called, called... I cannot remember but they were always pink and white... [PwD moves around, turned even back from his sit, points at stuff, laughs and acts happily] [PwD19, Observations]

After VR:

“R: How are you feeling? Did you enjoy it?

PwD: How nice, how nice, how nice, very nice, very nice. The flowers and the sky and the animals. How nice, how nice, how nice, very nice, very nice.” [PwD19, Interview]

3.1.1.1. Pain alleviation. Research has shown that pain is one of the most common symptoms among PwD, with up to 80 % of PwD suffering from pain regularly (Department of Health 2014; Lobbezoo et al., 2011;

Fig. 4. The image depicts the virtual environment that the PwD observed and discussed.

Maxwell et al., 2008; Shega et al., 2004; van t’Hof et al., 2011). Studies have described under-treatment of pain in dementia care (Morrison and Siu, 2000; Teno et al., 2001), which in the end is a causal factor of BPSD, and especially causative for agitation, aggression, and psychosis (Maxwell et al., 2008; Achterberg et al., 2013; Corbett et al., 2012; Hall-Lord et al., 2003; Husebo et al., 2014). In light of the above, we verify that most of our participants reported being in pain and some of the participants refused to participate in the study because at that moment they were dealing with severe pain. However, in line with studies which suggest that VR can provide an alternative and advanced form of analgesia (Matsangidou et al., 2017), we found a negative correlation between the administration of VR and pain in PwD. This is because research on the neurobiological mechanisms has shown that VR can alter the perception of pain with the help of actions that are perceived by the subject in pain as withdrawing its attention from the painful sensory signal (Gold et al., 2007). This is because the individual’s attentional resources are limited; thus, the use of distraction (via VR) decreases the cognitive capacity the individual has to process painful incomes (McCaul and Malott, 1984). VR technology offers multi-sensory information that helps the person become fully immersed in the simulated world and thus distracted from the sensory signal of pain.

Previous research has also suggested that HR is a reliable measurement to indicate pain (Forte et al., 2022; Matsangidou et al., 2020) since people in pain are usually having an elevated HR as well. Our data support these findings. Fig. 5 depicts the HR changes over time of a PwD who initially reported high levels of pain (and therefore a high HR was detected), but as the session progressed the PwD forgot about the pain (and so a HR reduction occurred accordingly).

Before VR exposure:

“PwD: I don’t want to do or try anything. I am in so much pain.

R: Why? What happened?

PwD: I fell over my wheelchair.

R: I have something that might help you feel a bit better.

PwD: mmm [looks upset and unsure]

R: Shall we at least try?

PwD: Do whatever you want. I am just waiting for my death to come.” [PwD11, Interview]

During VR exposure (see Fig. 6 for the appropriate setting):

“PwD: oh! Look at the beach, there is a passing boat, there are sailors on the boat, oh here is a small island far – far away, is it Ithaca? A boat that is going to Ithaca. Look at the wooden deck and the flowers around me and [He starts to sing a rhythmic song about the sea] sea – sea and salty waves [...] what a blessing, oh what a blessing you have given to me. Oh, my heart is young again!” [PwD11, Observations]

During the VR exposure, PwD referred to Ithaca which is a Greek island well known in Odyssey mythology as the island home of the hero Odysseus. Ithaca has an important meaning due to its symbolic value within the Odyssey mythology as it represents Odysseus’ love for his home, family, and an end to his long and arduous journey. We believe that the PwD reference to Ithaca was not arbitrary, but instead, he liked something from his inner desires.

After VR:

“R: So how are you feeling?

PwD: What have you done to me... You made my heart young again. You gave me a reason to live up to.

R: And what about the pain?

PwD: Which pain [giggles]. I forgot that I was in pain.

Fig. 5. The figure presents the elevated HR of the PwD while being in pain (areas with an orange background) and the sharp decrease in HR once the PwD got distracted from the virtual scenery (areas with white background).

Fig. 6. The image depicts the virtual environment that the PwD observed and discussed.

R: Do you now feel any pain?

PwD: [giggles] Not really.

R: And which island did you see in those glasses?

PwD: Ithaca! [his tone is confident and happy] Did I visit Ithaca?

R: What do you think?

PwD: I think it was Ithaca.

R: Why Ithaca?

PwD: I think it was Ithaca.

R: Whose island was Ithaca?

PwD: [laughs] The great Odysseus" [PwD11, Interview]

3.1.1.2. Reminiscence therapy. When treating dementia, it is recommended to consider reminiscence therapy as a strength-based, person-centred approach (Saredakis et al., 2021). Reminiscence therapy involves recalling memories through experiencing and discussing past events and using familiar objects to aid in the process (Woods et al., 2018). Through this therapy, the goal is to integrate both positive and negative aspects of one's past into a meaningful life story and ultimately redefine negative interpretations of PwD's past (World Health Organization (WHO), 2021). The recall of memories (either positive or negative) may cause some sort of distress for the PwD (Wong and Watt, 1991; Cappeliez et al., 2008); however, to the best of our knowledge, up to date no harm has been reported by the reminiscence therapy (Woods et al., 2018). In line with the above, we found that during and after the VR exposure, PwD reminisced about their hometowns and villages, places they visited, or even more intimate stuff like their backyard, etc. Even though the system was not fully personalized, we managed through the thorough VE selection process (see Matsangidou et al. 2022)

to meet the PwD interests and memories.

In line with previous research (Siriraya and Ang, 2014; Tabbai et al., 2019; Rose et al., 2021) we found that PwD are reminded of a memory from their past once similar elements to that memory appears. For example, the presence of the lake, along with some vehicles racing around, reminded a PwD of his accident which confined him to a wheelchair. It is worth mentioning that, during the moment that memory occurred, the PwD's HR raised at least 20 beats per minute (bpm), but once the PwD turned his attention toward the water his HR reduced back to normal. According to studies (Cohen et al., 2000; Harvey et al., 2012), when PwD recall their trauma, their heart rate tends to increase due to stressful reimagining, while other studies (Baillon et al., 2004; Cotelli et al., 2012) indicated that HR can decrease when reminiscence therapy is applied. It appears that our findings support this statement since we observed that both positive (i.e., swimming in the sea) and negative (i.e., car accident) aspects of PwD's past integrated during the exposure resulted in a meaningful life story. Fig. 7 schematically presents the HR changes over time based on where the PwD was looking as recorded using the eye-tracking system.

During VR exposure (see Fig. 1 for the appropriate setting):

"PwD: The birds flying around, bringing messages and greetings. The trees are green and there is sand [bends down to touch the sand] right under my feet! Ohh what a blessing, it is so beautiful! And look far-far way, there is a car, with four wheels, and another car with four wheels, all the cars got four wheels, I don't like four-wheeled cars, I used to have a two-wheeled [≈ motorbike]. [Heart rate starting to raise] I had a beautiful two-wheeled car and I was riding free and then I fall off and broke my legs and now I got 12 screws in each leg, and I can barely walk, I am stuck in this chair [His voice is breaking, and his heart rate has raised close to 100bpm, then he looks at the beach and his heart rate drops back to normal]. I think I am going to start crying, I am stuck in this chair far away from my beloved sea, but at least with these glasses, I can see the sea. Can I keep the glasses? Please let me keep the glasses so each time I miss the sea I can visit it..." [PwD11, Observations]

3.1.1.2. Blending the real with the unreal

Throughout our study, we noted a range of reactions from PwD. Based on our analysis, we have identified three sub-themes that can be used to inform the design of VR applications intended for PwD: (a) Stuck in a loop; (b) Transitioning between the two worlds; and (c) the role of caregivers in the multiverse.

3.1.1.2.1. Stuck in a loop. Looping is very common for PwD and it involves the repeating of stories or fixations. Looping is often described in association with BPSD, and especially agitation, as repetitiveness is one of the core symptoms (Hwang et al., 2000; Tractenberg et al., 2002). Based on previous literature, looping is measured by the repetition of words, the frequency of repeated words or similarity between sentences as well as the repeating topics (Fraser et al., 2016; Cook et al., 2009).

Fig. 7. The HR of a PwD while they experience a VE and recall a memory of a car accident in their youth. The figure presents the sharp increase in the HR once the PwD looked at a car racing (areas with orange background) and then the sharp decrease once the PwD looked back at the water (areas with blue background).

During our experiment, PwD were constantly looping by fixating on objects in view. It is worth mentioning that in all cases PwD were fixating on objects which were associated with positive emotions.

During VR exposure:

“PwD: Oh, look at the sky, it is clear and blue, the flowers are red and white, the donkey is rolling on the grass... [A couple of seconds later] Oh, look at the sky, the flowers are red and white... [A couple of seconds later] Ohhh, the flowers are red and white... [A couple of seconds later] Oh, look at the flowers are red and white... [A couple of seconds later] Oh look at the flowers are red and white” [PwD2, Observations]

Previous literature suggests that looping in dementia, based on repetitive phenomena and fixed patterns, is considered to be an early sign or a valid predictor of dementia (Baumgarten et al., 1990; Teri et al., 1992; Gauthier et al., 1997; Tariot et al., 1995; Hwang et al., 1997). Even though VR is still a relatively new and understudied solution, it is actively used in diagnostics of several neurological diseases (Slyk et al., 2019). The exaggerated looping patterns of the PwD during the VR exposure suggest that VR may be useful for dementia diagnosis in the future.

3.1.2.2. Transitioning between the two worlds. In general, PwD might experience disorientation in place and time, and previous literature has documented that VR exposure can increase the sense of disorientation in space (Tabbaa et al., 2019; Matsangidou et al., 2020). Our study observations align with the previous finding, as some PwD could not distinguish between the virtual and the physical space.

During VR exposure:

“R: Where are you?”

PwD: At the mountains [with specific tone]” [PwD6, Observations]

After the VR exposure:

“PwD: Where are we?”

R: Where do you think?”

PwD: [PwD looks around, thinks a bit, then looks out of the window, spots a tree] at the mountains [her tone is unsure]” [PwD6, Interview]

We believe that the deployment of VR in dementia care must incorporate a smooth transitioning process between the physical and the virtual space. It is worth examining the use of the passthrough feature of modern VR headsets to ease the transition from the virtual space and to sensitively re-direct the PwD back to “reality”.

3.1.2.3. The role of caregivers in the multiverse. In line with the previous findings (see theme: transitioning between the two words), we also observed the vital role of the caregiver (or even the presence of a person

who will be in the room with the PwD during the VR session). We suggest that the deployment have a caregiver able to assist the transitioning from the physical to the virtual world and back. Also, we observed that most of the PwD interacted with the researchers in the physical room during exposure.

During VR exposure:

“PwD: Look! Look! The car is passing through! [PwD laughs], and I can also hear the birds! Where are the birds? [R didn't respond, PwD repeated in agony, indicating that a response is required] Where are the birds?”

R: They are flying up to the sky. Look up!

PwD: [PwD turns her head up to the sky and bursts into laughter] Oh, here they are!” [PwD10, Observations]

“PwD: Is this the [named a specific] lake? Excuse me, do you hear me?”

R: Yes, we do.

PwD: Which lake is it? Is it the [Name] lake?”

R: Yes, it is.

PwD: I grew up close to that lake. Are you here? Do you listen to me?” [PwD4, Observations]

Despite the common preconception that VR is an isolating experience (Pringle, 2017) and in line with a study that examined the appropriate types of VR for PwD (Hodge et al., 2018), we believe that VR can be a space to facilitate social interactions. Additionally, studies suggested that VR can help patients open up and communicate their feelings (Matsangidou et al., 2022; Blythe et al., 2010). Based on our observations, we trust that the feeling of togetherness enhances VR's therapeutic role and VR is a critical intervention which can enhance the establishment of the therapeutic alliance (Gorini et al., 2007; 2008). It is important to note that positive therapeutic outcomes are correlated with the therapeutic alliance or relationship between the therapist and the patient (Flückiger et al., 2018) and as for PwD, previous research has shown that social support and a sense of belongingness can help PwD to improve their resilience coping mechanisms, thereby reducing BPSD and especially anxiety and depression (Kelley, 1997; Lee et al., 2017; Campo and Chaudhury, 2012).

3.1.3. Material properties and interactivity

Our analysis, identified the key aspects and functions necessary for the successful VR system design. These can be summarized into the following sub-themes: (a) Feasibility and acceptability of technology; (b) Material properties; and (c) Augmentation of self: neural impulses and interactions.

3.1.3.1. Feasibility and acceptability of technology. Even though a couple

of years ago, it was not clear whether VR can be a feasible solution for PwD, several studies documented the feasibility and acceptability of VR when deployed into healthcare units with plenty of positive results (Rose et al., 2018; Matsangidou et al., 2022; Siriaraya and Ang, 2014; Tabbaa et al., 2019; Matsangidou et al., 2022; 2020). In line with the above findings, we can confidently advise that VR is a feasible and well-tolerated technology by PwD. However, in most cases, it requires a significant amount of time from the nursing staff to deploy the system into the healthcare setting. Therefore, choosing a technology that is portable and easy to set up in hospital environments is essential. Especially when working with PwD who are facing BPSD and can easily be upset, a speedy and easy setup is a crucial factor to avoid PwD experiencing any type of discomfort.

Familiarization with the equipment is also a vital factor when dealing with PwD. As PwD are facing BPSD and usually are dealing with high levels of anxiety and fear. Previous studies suggested a reluctance to wear the VR headset due to the fear of the unknown (Matsangidou et al., 2020). Even though our participants were exposed for the first time to VR and therefore, the unfamiliarity of this technology could have made the PwD sceptical, however, such reactions were not observed as we spend a significant amount of time familiarizing the PwD with the equipment and the intervention. We believe that familiarizing themselves with the equipment made the PwD less anxious and more willing to try the technology.

Lastly, personalization is a key factor when dealing with older adults. In line with past studies, a special focus should be placed on creating personalized experiences that consider the preferences and capabilities of each PwD (Rose et al., 2018; Appel et al., 2016; Woods et al., 2018; Manera et al., 2015). For example, some PwD were unable to listen to the system's sounds and/or view objects far in proximity. Therefore, during the VR exposure researchers had to adjust the audio-visual content based on the PwD capabilities and needs.

During VR exposure:

“PwD: Why the birds aren't singing?”

R: Can't you hear them tweeting?”

PwD: What have you done to the birds why they are not singing? [We noticed that the PwD seems to be upset, so we decided to raise the volume] OH now I can hear them, [...] nice birdies, happy birdies!” [PwD8, Observations]

3.1.3.2. Material properties. In contrast to other kinds of technologies, such as flat-screen interfaces, the fully-immersive VR systems envelop the users' view completely. Therefore, and due to the material aspects of the system (i.e., worn on the head) two out of twenty PwD (all women), reported being uncomfortable with the system.

During VR exposure:

“PwD: These glasses are too heavy and are making it hard for me to breathe.

R: Shall we remove the glasses?”

PwD: No.

R: [A bit later] How are you feeling? Shall we remove the glasses?”

PwD: No, I am happy in here.

R: But is it heavy?”

PwD: Yes, and it is difficult to breathe.

R: Shall we remove them then?”

PwD: No.” [PwD1, Observations]

Observations of such responses among PwD are not uncommon. According to previous research, handheld systems (i.e., holding the

HMD with their hands) are preferred by people with mild dementia (Hodge et al., 2018; Tabbaa et al., 2019). However, the physical capacity of some of the PwD (e.g., those suffering from Parkinson's disease or osteoarthritis), makes such a solution impractical. In line with a recent study on VR physical rehabilitation and dementia (Matsangidou et al., 2020), an exoskeleton could be a feasible and practical solution which can increase PwDs' tolerance and acceptance of VR.

3.1.3.3. Augmentation of self: neural impulses and interactions. In the past, some studies explored the use of embodied interactions by providing PwD with interactive virtual avatars. Their findings suggested that for people with mild dementia embodied interactions resulted in a greater sense of engagement (Manera et al., 2015; Zuidema et al., 2007). Based on our observations, most of the PwD, including people with mild, moderate and severe dementia, tried to physically interact with the system. For example, some PwD tried to put their feet into the water, others tried to cut a flower and touch the grass, while a PwD subject to paranoid schizophrenia tried to pet the cat which was in the virtual space (see Fig. 8 for the appropriate settings).

During VR exposure:

“PwD: Hey kitty – kitty come, come... [PwD lean forward trying to pet the kitten] Kitty – kitty come, come... kitty – kitty come, come... kitty – kitty come, come... kitty – kitty come, come...” [PwD12, Observations]

“PwD: OHHH! OHHH! [PwD shouted in excitement and pushed the chair back to look towards the back-right and then the back-left side] OH! OHHH! Grr, Grr, [...] Grass! [PwD tried to touch the grass with her foot] [PwD16, Observations]

After VR exposure:

“R: What did you like?”

PwD: Let me tell you something. Life is a collection of images and memories, and you, my lady, have given me so many. You, my lady, have given me life [...] I am saving the images we saw today, so I can save life [...] I was miserable today and this gave me joy [...] I was miserable today, but now I am not [...] I wish I could have this every single day.

R: So, you liked it. Is there anything else that needs to be done, to make it better?”

PwD: I would love to be able to touch the flowers. Will you let me touch the flowers?” [PwD3, Interviews]

Apart from the need for interactivity, PwD also reflected the need for multi-user / metaverse experiences. Metaverse is considered a post-reality universe where social interactions can be held by merging physical and virtual reality. Based on a previous study, PwD are suffering from loneliness which can be a predictor of the condition worsening (Sutin et al., 2020), as well as a factor for increasing BPSD (Lyketsos et al., 2011). Most of our participants suggested that they would enjoy the presence of their family, as they reported intensely missing them.

After VR exposure:

“R: What did you like?”

PwD: In there [point to the VR headset] I was feeling happy, but now I feel a bit sad again.

R: Is there anything we can do to make you feel better?”

PwD: [PwD was immersed into the living room] Can you bring my son? I would like to be with him in the living room, I would like to have him by my side while listening to that nice music.

R: Would that be enough? Just having him in there? [R pointed to the VR headset]

Fig. 8. The image depicts the virtual environment that the PwD observed and discussed. On the left the virtual environment where a PwD and paranoid schizophrenia tried to pet the cat, while on the right the virtual environment where some PwD tried touch the grass.

PwD: More than enough, that will be the absolute happiness” [PwD1, Interviews]

An experience in the metaverse is characterized by a sense of presence, which combines the illusion of non-mediation, which means that the user can perceive the self in a space without being aware of the mediator technology that is responsible for its creation. We believe that PwD were experiencing in some sense the metaverse and so they requested for their relatives to join them in the virtual space without being able to distinguish between the real and the virtual.

4. Implications and recommendations

The findings of this study demonstrate several important advancements in the use of VR as a DTx tool for PwD, particularly in addressing BPSD. By leveraging immersive virtual environments, we observed significant reductions in symptoms such as aggression, agitation, anxiety, and depression. Moreover, the integration of real-time physiological monitoring through HR and eye-tracking data provided objective evidence that supports the emotional and behavioral benefits observed during VR sessions. VR experiences further amplified these positive outcomes, as PwD were able to engage with environments that evoked personal memories, enhancing both emotional well-being and cognitive stimulation. Additionally, the study opens new avenues for future applications of VR in dementia diagnosis, based on behavioral patterns such as looping. Finally, the potential for multi-user VR environments, where PwD could interact with family members, presents a novel possibility to mitigate loneliness and improve HRQoL. We believe that these findings offer valuable insights into the growing role of VR in both therapeutic and diagnostic contexts for dementia care, warranting further exploration and development in future studies. Below, we discuss in detail the implications and recommendations that emerge from our findings, which have facilitated the successful design of VR systems for PwD.

The study verified prior research that VR can be a feasible solution for supporting PwD. Even beyond that, however, it has shown the positive effects it may have on the emotional well-being of the population. The data collected through qualitative methods confirms that the use of VR may improve BPSD for PwD. The positive effects were also validated through quantitative measures. As shown in Section 3.1.1 the recording and analysis of physiological data allows for a better understanding of the emotional state of PwD during VR exposure. Analysis of these data revealed a significant decrease in HR while participants were exposed to VR, supporting the observation that exposure to VR may effectively reduce pain and BPSD such as agitation, aggression, depression, and apathy in PwD.

Pain and BPSD symptoms are a major cause of distress for PwD and their caregivers, and are also linked to poor HRQoL (Selbæk et al., 2013; Zuidema et al., 2007; Ballard et al., 2001). Hence, the positive effects of VR on BPSD are crucial, as they may contribute to an improved HRQoL for PwD. These findings could be explained by referencing previous

research recognizing that being locked into a hospital environment can negatively affect the levels of BPSD the PwD are experiencing. To reduce BPSD and improve the HRQoL, exposure to out-reach and low-stimulus experiences have been suggested from the general literature (Canatsey and Roper, 1997; Chou et al., 2002; Waller and Masterson, 2015).

When considering the VR content design, we suggest taking into consideration the medical history of the PwD, paying particular attention to the BPSD symptoms each PwD experiences. For example, for PwD who are experiencing agitation, aggression, and/or depression, we suggest enhance the VR with content that is able to reduce the sense of loneliness. On this note our findings highlight the importance of social presence. An often request was the ability to experience the virtual environments along with family members or friends. PwD living at long-care homes are often isolated and miss connections from their past. This can be detrimental to their well-being causing depression or an increase in agitated behaviours (Azevedo et al., 2021). Multi-user experiences, and the connection with loved ones, can alleviate feelings of loneliness and reduce BPSD improving the HRQoL of PwD (Appel et al., 2021).

Furthermore, social presence plays a pivotal role in enhancing the acceptance and effectiveness of digital interventions, particularly for older adults who may be hesitant to adopt new technologies (Biocca et al., 2003). To encourage the use of VR in this population, it is essential to design human-centered applications that emphasize social presence (Kim and Song, 2024). This can be achieved through group-based activities or by incorporating avatars that closely mimic real human behaviors and communication. Research has shown that social presence in VR has a positive effect on PwD, and future developments should focus on improving these experiences with features such as lifelike avatars, synchronized lip movements, and natural body motions (Kothgassner et al., 2018; McGlynn and Rogers, 2017; Latoschik et al., 2017; Matsangidou et al., 2019).

On a similar note, many of the participants in our study claimed to be feeling homesick and so addressing this issue by implementing specific interventions is of major importance. This is in line with a previous study which suggested that PwD might be interested in visiting their own homes (Allen and Tulich, 2015). We feel that VR may overcome the limitations of hospital boundaries and offer the PwD such a possibility. Therefore, as part of future designs, we suggest including home-related environments to meet these needs.

Research has also indicated that PwD may exhibit agitation and aggression because of their surroundings and lack of privacy. Hospital settings have been shown to increase the likelihood of such behaviors. To create a more serene environment, it has been recommended to offer ample space, access to natural elements, and low-stimulation surroundings (Canatsey and Roper, 1997; Chou et al., 2002; Waller and Masterson, 2015). In line with a recent study (Tabbaa et al., 2019), our findings suggest that VR can be utilized to create a private and isolated space for PwD. In particular, our findings support the reduction of aggregated behaviours during and after VR exposure. Our research also

confirms the benefits of experiencing pleasant environments in private settings for PwD.

At the same time, it has been shown that VR has the potential to reduce anxiety and depression, especially when there is a greater sense of presence (Wang et al., 2022). For example, during our study, it has been observed that PwD often attempted to touch virtual objects in their environment, such as grass. To enrich their experience, incorporating physical interactions and reactions into the design can be quite beneficial. For instance, when an individual touches water, it could cause ripples, or when someone pets an animal, there can be a corresponding reaction. Such actions can create a highly immersive experience, resulting in better outcomes for BPSD.

Similarly, and by addressing the suggestion of out-reach experiences enhanced by nature, our findings also advise the design to add nature-related environments. Based on previous research, nature viewing can enhance emotional well-being and aid recovery from stress (Chalfont, 2007; Hendriks et al., 2016). Indeed, nature was the most chosen virtual environments for the PwD and based on our findings, nature was also able to reduce HR during distressing moments (e.g., a PwD was reminded of his motorbike accident and HR elevated, but when focused on the sea, the HR dropped), a finding that is also suggested by previous literature (Maller et al., 2006).

Another symptom with high prevalence among PwD, is the display of apathetic behaviors (Selbæk et al., 2013; Zuidema et al., 2007; Ballard et al., 2001). Our findings suggested that travelling is effective for PwD, since travel-related environments were found to reduce HR and such apathetic behaviors. In addition, and in accordance with previous research, PwD themselves, expressed a desire to travel and experience distant destinations (Asghar et al., 2020; Bauer, 2019). Thus, we suggest incorporating scenes of islands and/or cities into the VR design.

Elaborating on the above and by being consistent with previous studies, we found that PwD reminisced through the similarity and resemblance of environments (Siriraya and Ang, 2014), this is an important finding when treating dementia as, it is recommended to consider reminiscence therapy as a person-centred approach (Saredakis et al., 2021). Even though the system was not fully personalized, we managed to use familiar elements to meet the PwD memories. Therefore, for the successful design of VR for PwD, aged elements are essential, since they trigger memories of their past.

5. Conclusions

It is widely acknowledged that supporting the HRQoL of PwD, including their mental health and well-being, is crucial. Recent research indicates that VR can be a reliable, feasible, and acceptable solution that promotes engagement and provides an enjoyable experience for PwD (Rose et al., 2018; Appel et al., 2021). In line with the above out research underscores the significance of factors such as ease of setup, equipment familiarity, and personalization. It emphasizes the necessity for portable, easily deployable VR systems tailored to the specific requirements of PwD, particularly those facing BPSD. Also, familiarizing PwD with the equipment shows promise in mitigating anxiety and reluctance, fostering greater receptivity to the technology. Personalizing audio-visual content is integral to ensuring a comfortable and engaging experience aligned with individuals' capabilities. Further to the above, our research shows that VR may improve the HRQoL of PwD, as it offers several therapeutic benefits for this group. Specifically, the study highlighted the various ways that VR could be used to benefit PwD. For example, it can be used as a solution for pain management and relief, and as a tool to facilitate reminiscence therapy. Recalling memories can have multiple benefits, as shown in prior research (Bauer, 2019; Thomas and Sezgin, 2021), especially for people staying at long-care facilities. This was observed through the interactions of participants in this study as well. In addition, VR could also have a role in assisting the diagnosis of dementia, which can be achieved through the detection of patterns often observed in PwD, such as looping patterns or more

in-depth analysis of eye tracking data and gaze patterns (Tominari et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021). Research in these areas has only recently started, especially in relation to VR, and requires further exploration in the future. To rigorously assess the long-term sustainability of these positive outcomes, a longitudinal study with quantitative data and a control group is essential. Additionally, further research is needed to evaluate the potential benefits of VR for older adults with general cognitive impairment or those experiencing social isolation. Furthermore, areas for future research include incorporating embodied interaction, utilizing multi-user experiences to increase social presence, and integrating physiological and biometric data to better personalize VR content for PwD. Ultimately, we hope that our study sheds light on how VR technology can be designed, deployed, and used in the realm of dementia care and advocate for its utilization as a therapeutic tool.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Maria Matsangidou: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Theodoros Solomou:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Fotos Frangoudes:** Writing – review & editing, Software. **Ersi Papayianni:** Supervision, Resources. **Natalie Kkeli:** Supervision. **Constantinos S. Pattichi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Maria Matsangidou, Fotos Frangoudes reports financial support was provided by CYENS Centre of Excellence Ltd. Maria Matsangidou, Fotos Frangoudes reports financial support was provided by European Commission. Maria Matsangidou, Fotos Frangoudes, Constantinos S. Pattichi reports a relationship with CYENS Centre of Excellence Ltd that includes: employment and funding grants. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 739578 and the Government of the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

References

- Achterberg, W.P., Marjoleine, J.C.P., Annelore, H., van Dalen-Kok, M.W.M.D.W., Bettina, S., Husebo, S.L., Miriam, K., Scherder, E.J.A., Corbett, A., 2013. Pain management in patients with dementia. *Clin. Interv. Aging* 8, 1471. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CIA.S36739>.
- Allen, J., Tulich, T., 2015. I want to go home now: restraint decisions for dementia patients in Western Australia. *Law Context* 33 (2), 1–23.
- Alzheimer's Society of Canada. 2019. Conversations about: dementia and responsive behaviours. Retrieved September 14, 2022, from: https://alzheimer.ca/sites/default/files/documents/conversations_dementia-and-responsive-behaviours.pdf.
- Alzheimer's Research UK. 2024. Sea Hero Quest – a mobile game to help dementia research. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from: <https://www.alzheimersresearchuk.org/research/for-researchers/resources-and-information/sea-hero-quest/>.
- Anthony, J.C., LeResche, L., Niaz, U., Von Korff, M.R., Folstein, M.F., 1982. Limits of the 'Mini-Mental State' as a screening test for dementia and delirium among hospital patients. *Psychol. Med.* 12 (2), 397–408. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291700046730>.

- Anttonen, J., Surakka, V., 2005. Emotions and heart rate while sitting on a chair. In: Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, pp. 491–499. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1054972.1055040>.
- Appel, L., Kisonas, E., Appel, E., Klein, J., Bartlett, D., Rosenberg, J., Smith, C.N.C., 2016. Administering virtual reality therapy to manage behavioral and psychological symptoms in patients with dementia admitted to an acute care hospital: results of a pilot study. *JMIR Form. Res.* 5 (2). <https://doi.org/10.2196/22406>.
- Appel, L., Kisonas, E., Appel, E., Klein, J., Bartlett, D., Rosenberg, J., Smith, C., 2020. Introducing virtual reality therapy for inpatients with dementia admitted to an acute care hospital: learnings from a pilot to pave the way to a randomized controlled trial. Pilot and feasibility studies. *Study* 6 (1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40814-020-00708-9>.
- Appel, L., Ali, S., Narag, T., Mozeson, K., Pasat, Z., Orchanian-Cheff, A., Campos, J.L., 2021. Virtual reality to promote wellbeing in persons with dementia: a scoping review. *J. Rehabil. Assist. Technol. Eng.* 8. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20556683211053952>.
- Asghar, I., Cang, S., Yu, H., 2020. An empirical study on assistive technology supported travel and tourism for the people with dementia. *Disabil. Rehabil. Assist. Technol.* 15 (8), 933–944. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17483107.2019.1629119>.
- Azevedo, L.V.S., Calandri, I.L., Slachevsky, A., Graviotto, H.G., Vieira, M.C.S., Andrade, C.B., Rossetti, A.P., Generoso, A.B., Carmona, K.C., Pinto, L.A.C., Sorbara, M., Pinto, A., Guajardo, T., Olavarria, L., Thumala, D., Crivelli, L., Vivas, L., Allegrí, R.F., Barbosa, M.T., Serrano, C.M., Miranda-Castillo, C., Caramelli, P., 2021. Impact of social isolation on people with dementia and their family caregivers. *J. Alzheimer's Dis.* 81 (2), 607–617. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-201580>.
- Baillon, S., Van Diepen, E., Prettyman, R., Redman, J., Rooke, N., Campbell, R., 2004. A comparison of the effects of Snoezelen and reminiscence therapy on the agitated behaviour of patients with dementia. *Int. J. Geriatr. Psychiatry* 19 (11), 1047–1052. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gps.1208>.
- Ballard, C., O'Brien, J., James, I., Mynt, P., Lana, M., Potkins, D., Reichelt, K., Lee, L., Swann, A., Fossey, J., 2001. Quality of life for people with dementia living in residential and nursing home care: the impact of performance on activities of daily living, behavioral and psychological symptoms, language skills, and psychotropic drugs. *Int. Psychogeriatr.* 13 (1), 93–106. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1041610201007499>.
- Banerjee, S., Hellier, J., Dewey, M., Romeo, R., Ballard, C., Baldwin, R., Burns, A., 2011. Study of the use of anti-depressants for depression in dementia: the HTA-SADD Trial – a multicentre randomised double-blind, placebo-controlled trial of the clinical effectiveness of sertraline and mirtazapine. *Health Technol. Assess.* 17, 1–166. <https://doi.org/10.3310/hta17070> (Rockv).
- S. Banerjee 2009. The use of antipsychotic medication for people with dementia: time for action. Report for the Minister of State for Care Services. Retrieved from: <http://psychrights.org/research/digest/nlps/banerjeeereportongeriatricneurolepticuse.pdf>.
- Bauer, J.L., 2019. Caregivers of travelers with dementia—a neglected travel population. *J. Travel. Med.* 26 (7), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jtm/taz061>.
- Baumgarten, M., Becker, R., Gauthier, S., 1990. Validity and reliability of the dementia behavior disturbance scale. *J. Am. Geriatr. Soc.* 38 (3), 221–226. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1532-5415.1990.tb03495.x>.
- Biocca, F., Harms, C., Burgoon, J.K., 2003. Toward a more robust theory and measure of social presence: review and suggested criteria. *Presence Teleoper. Virtual Environ.* 12 (5), 456–480. <https://doi.org/10.1162/105474603322761270>.
- Blythe, M., Wright, P., Bowers, J., Boucher, A., Jarvis, N., Reynolds, P., Gaver, B., 2010. Age and experience: ludic engagement in a residential care setting. In: Proceedings of the 8th ACM Conference on Designing Interactive Systems, pp. 161–170. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1858171.1858200>.
- Botella, C., Fernández-Álvarez, J., Guillén, V., García-Palacios, A., Baños, R., 2017. Recent progress in virtual reality exposure therapy for phobias: a systematic review. *Curr. Psychiatry Rep.* 19 (7), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11920-017-0788-4>.
- Braun, U., Clarke, V., 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual. Res. Psychol.* 3 (2), 77–101.
- Campo, M., Chaudhury, H., 2012. Informal social interaction among residents with dementia in special care units: exploring the role of the physical and social environments. *Dementia* 11 (3), 401–423. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1471301211421189>.
- Canatsey, K., Roper, J.M., 1997. Removal from stimuli for crisis intervention: using least restrictive methods to improve the quality of patient care. *Issues Ment. Health Nurs.* 18 (1), 35–44. <https://doi.org/10.3109/01612849709006538>.
- Cappeliez, P., Guindon, M., Robitaille, A., 2008. Functions of reminiscence and emotional regulation among older adults. *J. Aging Stud.* 22 (3), 266–272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaging.2007.06.003>.
- Chalfont, G., 2007. *Design for Nature in Dementia Care*. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Chou, K.R., Lu, R.B., Mao, W.C., 2002. Factors relevant to patient assaultive behavior and assault in acute inpatient psychiatric units in Taiwan. *Arch. Psychiatr. Nurs.* 16 (4), 187–195. <https://doi.org/10.1053/apnu.2002.34394>.
- Clus, D., Erik Larsen, M., Lemey, C., Berrouiguet, S., 2018. The use of virtual reality in patients with eating disorders: systematic review. *J. Med. Internet Res.* 20 (4). <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.7898>.
- Cohen, H., Benjamin, J., Geva, A.B., Matar, M.A., Kaplan, Z., Kotler, M., 2000. Autonomic dysregulation in panic disorder and in post-traumatic stress disorder: application of power spectrum analysis of heart rate variability at rest and in response to recollection of trauma or panic attacks. *Psychiatry Res.* 96 (1), 1–13. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0165-1781\(00\)00195-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0165-1781(00)00195-5).
- Cook, C., Fay, S., Rockwood, K., 2009. Verbal repetition in people with mild-to-moderate Alzheimer disease: a descriptive analysis from the VISTA Clinical Trial. *Alzheimer Dis. Assoc. Disord.* 23 (2), 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.1097/WAD.0b013e318193cbef>.
- Corbett, A., Husebo, B., Malcangio, M., Staniland, A., Cohen-Mansfield, J., Aarsland, D., Ballard, C., 2012. Assessment and treatment of pain in people with dementia. *Nat. Rev. Neurol.* 8 (5), 264–274. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrneuro.2012.53>.
- Cotelli, M., Manenti, R., Zanetti, O., 2012. Reminiscence therapy in dementia: a review. *Maturitas* 72 (3), 203–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.maturitas.2012.04.008>.
- Cushman, L.A., Stein, K., Duffy, C.J., 2008. Detecting navigational deficits in cognitive aging and Alzheimer disease using virtual reality. *Neurology* 71 (12), 888–895. <https://doi.org/10.1212/01.wnl.0000326262.67613.fe>.
- D' Cunha, N.M., Nguyen, D., Naumovski, N., McKune, A.J., Kellett, J., Georgousopoulou, E.N., Frost, J., Isbel, S., 2019. A mini-review of virtual reality-based interventions to promote well-being for people living with dementia and mild cognitive impairment. *Gerontology* 65 (4), 430–440. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000500040>.
- Dang, A., Arora, D., Rane, P., 2020. Role of digital therapeutics and the changing future of healthcare. *J. Fam. Med. Prim. Care* 9 (5), 2207–2213. <https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc.105.20>.
- Department of Health. 2014. G8 dementia summit: global action against dementia – 11 December 2013. London: Department of Health.
- Doniger, G.M., Beer, M.S., Bahar-Fuchs, A., Gottlieb, A., Tkachov, A., Kenan, H., Livny, A., et al., 2018. Virtual reality-based cognitive-motor training for middle-aged adults at high Alzheimer's disease risk: a randomized controlled trial. *Alzheimer's Dement. Transl. Res. Clin. Interv.* 4, 118–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trci.2018.02.005>.
- Flückiger, C., Del Re, A.C., Wampold, B.E., Horvath, A.O., 2018. The alliance in adult psychotherapy: a meta-analytic synthesis. *Psychotherapy* 55 (4), 316. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pst0000172>.
- Fodor, L.A., Cote, C.D., Cuijpers, P., Szamoskozi, S., David, D., Cristea, I.A., 2018. The effectiveness of virtual reality based interventions for symptoms of anxiety and depression: a meta-analysis. *Sci. Rep.* 8 (1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-28113-6>, 2018.
- Forde, G., Troisi, G., Pazzaglia, M., Pascalis, V.D., Casagrande, M., 2022. Heart rate variability and pain: a systematic review. *Brain Sci.* 12 (2), 153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci12020153>.
- Fortune Business Insights. 2024. Digital therapeutics market size, share & COVID-19 impact analysis. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from: <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/digital-therapeutics-market-103501>.
- Fraser, K.C., Meltzer, J.A., Rudzicz, F., 2016. Linguistic features identify Alzheimer's disease in narrative speech. *J. Alzheimer's Dis.* 49 (2), 407–422. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-150520>.
- Gómez-Romero, M., Jiménez-Palomares, M., Rodríguez-Mansilla, J., Flores-Nieto, A., Garrido-Ardila, E.M., González-López-Arza, M.V., 2017. Benefits of music therapy on behaviour disorders in subjects diagnosed with dementia: a systematic review. *Neurología* 32 (4), 253–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nrleng.2014.11.003> (English Edition).
- Garg, M., Saluja, M., 2023. MT68 digital therapeutics (DTx) for Alzheimer's disease, dementia and mild cognitive impairment: a pragmatic review of clinical evidence. *Value Health* 26 (12), S439. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2023.09.2294>.
- Gauthier, S., Baumgarten, M., Becker, R., 1997. Dementia behavior disturbance scale. *Int. Psychogeriatr.* 8 (S3), 325–327. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1041610297003566>.
- Gold, J.I., Belmont, K.A., Thomas, D.A., 2007. The neurobiology of virtual reality pain attenuation. *CyberPsychol. Behav.* 10 (4), 536–544. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cpb.2007.9993>.
- Gorini, A., Gaggioli, A., Riva, G., 2007. Virtual worlds, real healing. *Science* 318 (5856), 1549. <https://doi.org/10.26481/dis.20100922ag>, New York then Washington.
- Gorini, A., Gaggioli, A., Riva, G., 2008. A second life for eHealth: prospects for the use of 3-D virtual worlds in clinical psychology. *J. Med. Internet Res.* 10 (3), e1029. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.1029>.
- Hall-Lord, M.L., Johansson, I., Schmidt, I., Larsson, B.W., 2003. Family members' perceptions of pain and distress related to analgesics and psychotropic drugs, and quality of care of elderly nursing home residents. *Health Soc. Care Community* 11 (3), 262–274. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2524.2003.00427.x>.
- J. Hardy and M. Scanlon 2009. *The science behind Lumosity*. San Francisco, CA: Lumosity Labs.
- Harvey, A., Bandiera, G., Nathens, A.B., LeBlanc, V.R., 2012. Impact of stress on resident performance in simulated trauma scenarios. *J. Trauma Acute Care Surg.* 72 (2), 497–503. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ta.0b013e31821f84be>.
- Hendriks, I.H., Vliet, D., Gerritsen, D.L., Dröes, R.M., 2016. Nature and dementia: development of a person-centered approach. *Int. Psychogeriatr.* 28 (9), 1455–1470. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1041610216000612>.
- Hodge, J., Balaam, M., Hastings, S., Morrissey, K., 2018. Exploring the design of tailored virtual reality experiences for people with dementia. In: Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (2018), pp. 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3173574.3174088>.
- Huang, L.C., Yang, Y.H., 2022. The long-term effects of immersive virtual reality reminiscence in people with dementia: longitudinal observational study. *JMIR Serious Games* 10 (3). <https://doi.org/10.2196/36720>.
- Husebo, B.S., Ballard, C., Cohen-Mansfield, J., Seifert, R., Aarsland, D., 2014. The response of agitated behavior to pain management in persons with dementia. *Am. J. Geriatr. Psychiatry* 22 (7), 708–717. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jagp.2012.12.006>.
- Hwang, J.P., Yang, C.H., Tsai, S.J., Liu, K.M., 1997. Behavioural disturbances in psychiatric inpatients with dementia of the Alzheimer's type in Taiwan. *Int. J. Geriatr. Psychiatry* 12 (9), 902–906. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1166\(199709\)12:9<902::AID-GPS660>3.0.CO;2-Q](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1166(199709)12:9<902::AID-GPS660>3.0.CO;2-Q).
- Hwang, J.P., Tsai, S.J., Yang, C.H., Liu, K.M., Lirng, J.F., 2000. Repetitive phenomena in dementia. *Int. J. Psychiatry Med.* 30 (2), 165–171. <https://doi.org/10.2190/2QDA-YAL3-2E69-PYJW>.

- Kales, H.C., Gitlin, L.N., Lyketsos, C.G., 2015. Assessment and management of behavioral and psychological symptoms of dementia. *BMJ* 350. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.h369>.
- Kasl-Godley, J., Gatz, M., 2000. Psychosocial interventions for individuals with dementia: an integration of theory, therapy, and a clinical understanding of dementia. *Clin. Psychol. Rev.* 20 (6), 755–782. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7358\(99\)00062-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7358(99)00062-8).
- Kelley, M.F., 1997. Social interaction among people with dementia. *J. Gerontol. Nurs.* 23 (4), 16–20. <https://doi.org/10.3928/0098-9134-19970401-10>.
- Kim, D., Song, H., 2024. Designing an age-friendly conversational AI agent for mobile banking: the effects of voice modality and lip movement. *Int. J. Hum. Comput. Stud.* 187, 103262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2024.103262>.
- Kishita, N., Backhouse, T., Mioshi, E., 2020. Nonpharmacological interventions to improve depression, anxiety, and quality of life (QoL) in people with dementia: an overview of systematic reviews. *J. Geriatr. Psychiatry Neurol.* 33 (1), 28–41. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891988719856690>.
- Kitwood, T.M., Kitwood, T.M., 1997. *Dementia Reconsidered: the Person Comes First*, 20. Open university press, Buckingham, 1997.
- Kothgassner, O.D., Goreis, A., Kafka, J.K., Hlavacs, H., Beutl, L., Kryspin-Exner, I., Felnhöfer, A., 2018. Agency and gender influence older adults' presence-related experiences in an interactive virtual environment. *Cyberpsychol. Behav. Soc. Netw.* 21 (5), 318–324. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2017.0691>.
- Latoschik, M.E., Roth, D., Gall, D., Achenbach, J., Waltemate, T., Botsch, M., 2017. The effect of avatar realism in immersive social virtual realities. In: Proceedings of the 23rd ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology, pp. 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3139131.3139156>.
- Lee, K.H., Boltz, M., Lee, H., Algase, D.L., 2017. Does social interaction matter psychological well-being in persons with dementia? *Am. J. Alzheimer's Dis. Other Dement.* 32 (4), 207–212. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1533317517704301>.
- Liu, Z., Yang, Z., Gu, Y., Liu, H., Wang, P., 2021. The effectiveness of eye tracking in the diagnosis of cognitive disorders: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One* 16 (7), e0254059. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254059>.
- Livingston, G., Kelly, L., Lewis-Holmes, E., Baio, G., Morris, S., Patel, N., Omar, R.Z., Katona, C., Cooper, C., 2014. Non-pharmacological interventions for agitation in dementia: systematic review of randomised controlled trials. *Br. J. Psychiatry* 205 (6), 436–442. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.113.141119>.
- Lobbezoo, F., Weijenberg, R.A.F., Scherder, E.J.A., 2011. Topical review: orofacial pain in dementia patients. A diagnostic challenge. *J. Oral Facial Pain* 25 (1), 6–14.
- Lyketsos, C.G., Carrillo, M.C., Michael Ryan, J., Khachaturian, A.S., Trzepacz, P., Amatniek, J., Cedarbaum, J., Brashear, R., Miller, D.S., 2011. Neuropsychiatric symptoms in Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's Dement.* 7 (5), 532–539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2011.05.2410>.
- Maller, C., Townsend, M., Pryor, A., Brown, P., Leger, LSt, 2006. Healthy nature healthy people: contact with nature as an upstream health promotion intervention for populations. *Health Promot. Int.* 21 (1), 45–54. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapro/dai032>.
- Manera, V., Petit, P.D., Derreumaux, A., Orvioto, I., Romagnoli, M., Lyttle, G., David, R., Robert, P.H., 2015. Kitchen and cooking, 'a serious game for mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease: a pilot study. *Front. Aging Neurosci.* 7, 24. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2015.00024>.
- Manera, V., Chapoulie, E., Bourgeois, J., Gourchouche, R., David, R., Ondrej, J., Drettakis, G., Robert, P., 2016. A feasibility study with image-based rendered virtual reality in patients with mild cognitive impairment and dementia. *PLoS One* 11 (3). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0151487>.
- Matsangidou, M., Siang Ang, C., Sakel, M., 2017. Clinical utility of virtual reality in pain management: a comprehensive research review. *Br. J. Neurosci. Nurs.* 13 (3), 133–143. <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjnn.2017.13.3.133>.
- Matsangidou, M., Siang Ang, C., Mauger, A.R., Intarasirisawat, J., Otkhmezuri, B., Avraamides, M.N., 2019. Is your virtual self as sensational as your real? Virtual reality: the effect of body consciousness on the experience of exercise sensations. *Psychol. Sport Exerc.* 41, 218–224.
- Matsangidou, M., Schiza, E., Hadjjaros, M., Neokleous, K.C., Avraamides, M., Papayianni, E., Frangoudes, F., Pattichis, C.S., 2020. Dementia: I am physically fading. Can virtual reality help? Physical training for people with dementia in confined mental health units. In: Proceedings of the International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction, pp. 366–382. [doi:10.1007/978-3-030-49282-3_26](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49282-3_26).
- Matsangidou, M., Mauger, A.R., Siang Ang, C., Pattichis, C.S., 2020. Sampling electrocardiography confirmation for a virtual reality pain management tool. In: *Virtual, Augmented and Mixed Reality. Industrial and Everyday Life Applications*, 22. Springer International Publishing, pp. 399–414. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49698-2_27, 12th International Conference, VAMR 2020, Held as Part of the 22nd HCI International Conference, HCII 2020, Copenhagen, Denmark, July 19–24, 2020, Proceedings, Part II.
- Matsangidou, M., Frangoudes, F., Hadjjaros, M., Schiza, E., Neokleous, K.C., Papayianni, E., Avraamides, M., Pattichis, C.S., 2022. "Bring me sunshine, bring me (physical) strength": the case of dementia. Designing and implementing a virtual reality system for physical training during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Int. J. Hum. Comput. Stud.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2022.102840>.
- Matsangidou, M., Frangoudes, F., Schiza, E., Neokleous, K.C., Papayianni, E., Xenari, K., Avraamides, M., Pattichis, C.S., 2022. Participatory design and evaluation of virtual reality physical rehabilitation for people living with dementia. *Virtual Real.* 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-022-00639-1>.
- Matsangidou, M., Frangoudes, F., Solomou, T., Papayianni, E., Pattichis, C., 2022. Free of walls: participatory design of an out-world experience via virtual reality for dementia in-patients. In: *Proceedings of the 30th ACM Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization*, pp. 326–334.
- Matsangidou, M., Otkhmezuri, B., Siang Ang, C., Avraamides, M., Riva, G., Gaggioli, A., Iosif, D., Karekla, M., 2022. Now i can see me" designing a multi-user virtual reality remote psychotherapy for body weight and shape concerns. *Hum. Comput. Interact.* 37 (4), 314–340. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07370024.2020.1788945>.
- Matsangidou, M., Solomou, T., Frangoudes, F., Ioannou, K., Theofanous, P., Papayianni, E., Pattichis, C.S., 2023. Affective out-world experience via virtual reality for older adults living with mild cognitive impairments or mild dementia. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 20 (4), 2919.
- Matsangidou, M., Solomou, T., Frangoudes, F., Papayianni, E., Pattichis, C.S., 2023. Offering outworld experiences to in-patients with dementia through virtual reality: mixed methods study. *JMIR Aging* 6 (1), e45799.
- Maxwell, C.J., Dalby, D.M., Slater, M., Patten, S.B., Hogan, D.B., Eliasziw, M., Hirdes, J.P., 2008. The prevalence and management of current daily pain among older home care clients. *Pain* 138 (1), 208–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pain.2008.04.007>.
- McCallum, S., Boletis, C., 2013. Dementia games: a literature review of dementia-related serious games. In: *Serious Games Development and Applications*, 2013. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Trondheim, Norway, pp. 15–27, 4th International Conference, SGDASeptember 25–27, 2013. Proceedings 4.
- McCaul, K.D., Malott, J.M., 1984. Distraction and coping with pain. *Psychol. Bull.* 95 (3), 516–533. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.95.3.516>.
- McGlynn, S.A., Rogers, W.A., 2017. Design recommendations to enhance virtual reality presence for older adults. In: *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, 61. SAGE Publications, Los Angeles, CA, pp. 2077–2081. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1541931213602002>.
- Morrison, R.S., Siu, A.L., 2000. A comparison of pain and its treatment in advanced dementia and cognitively intact patients with hip fracture. *J. Pain Symptom Manag.* 19 (4), 240–248. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-3924\(00\)00113-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-3924(00)00113-5).
- Optale, G., Urgesi, C., Busato, V., Marin, S., Piron, L., Piffrits, K., Gamberini, L., Capodici, S., Bordin, A., 2010. Controlling memory impairment in elderly adults using virtual reality memory training: a randomized controlled pilot study. *Neurorehabil. Neural Repair.* 24 (4), 348–357. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1545968309333328>.
- Park, K.M., Ku, J., Choi, S.H., Jang, H.J., Park, Ji-Y, Kim, S.I., Kim, J.J., 2011. A virtual reality application in role-plays of social skills training for schizophrenia: a randomized, controlled trial. *Psychiatry Res.* 189 (2), 166–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2011.04.003>.
- Parsons, T.D., Rizzo, A.A., 2008. Affective outcomes of virtual reality exposure therapy for anxiety and specific phobias: a meta-analysis. *J. Behav. Ther. Exp. Psychiatry* 39 (3), 250–261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbtep.2007.07.007>.
- Pelletier, I.C., Landreville, P., 2007. Discomfort and agitation in older adults with dementia. *BMC Geriatr.* 7 (1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2318-7-27>.
- R. Pringle 2017. Virtual reality is still too isolating to be 'the next big thing' in tech. *CBC News* 14.
- Replika. 2024 Replika's story: building the AI that cares. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from: <https://replika.ai/about/story>.
- Reynolds, L., Rodiek, S., Lininger, M., McCulley, M.A., 2018. Can a virtual nature experience reduce anxiety and agitation in people with dementia? *J. Hous. Elder.* 32 (2), 176–193. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02763893.2018.1431583>.
- Rose, V., Stewart, I., Jenkins, K., Ang, C.S., Matsangidou, M., 2018. A scoping review exploring the feasibility of virtual reality technology use with individuals living with dementia. In: *Proceedings of the ICAT-EGVE*, 2018, pp. 131–139. <https://doi.org/10.2312/egve.20181325>.
- Rose, V., Stewart, I., Jenkins, K.G., Tabbaa, L., Ang, C.S., Matsangidou, M., 2021. Bringing the outside in: the feasibility of virtual reality with people with dementia in an inpatient psychiatric care setting. *Dementia* 20 (1), 106–129.
- Rus-Calafell, M., Garety, P., Sason, E., Craig, T.J.K., Valmaggia, L.R., 2018. Virtual reality in the assessment and treatment of psychosis: a systematic review of its utility, acceptability and effectiveness. *Psychol. Med.* 48 (3), 362–391.
- Slyk, S., Zygmunt Zarzycki, M., Kocwa-Karnaś, A., Domitrz, I., 2019. Virtual reality in the diagnostics and therapy of neurological diseases. *Expert Rev. Med. Devices* 16 (12), 1035–1040. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17434440.2019.1693892>.
- Sampson, E.L., White, N., Leurent, B., Scott, S., Lord, K., Round, J., Jones, L., 2014. Behavioural and psychiatric symptoms in people with dementia admitted to the acute hospital: prospective cohort study. *Br. J. Psychiatry* 205 (3), 189–196. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.113.130948>.
- Saredakis, D., Keage, H.A.D., Corlis, M., Loetscher, T., 2020. Using virtual reality to improve apathy in residential aged care: mixed methods study. *J. Med. Internet Res.* 22 (6). <https://doi.org/10.2196/17632>.
- Saredakis, D., Keage, H.A.D., Corlis, M., Ghezzi, E.S., Löffler, H., Loetscher, T., 2021. The effect of reminiscence therapy using virtual reality on apathy in residential aged care: multisite nonrandomized controlled trial. *J. Med. Internet Res.* 23 (9). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-046030>.
- Saredakis, D., Keage, H.A.D., Corlis, M., Loetscher, T., 2021. Virtual reality intervention to improve apathy in residential aged care: protocol for a multisite non-randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Open* 11 (2). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-046030>.
- Savva, G.M., Zaccai, J., Matthews, F.E., Davidson, J.E., McKeith, I., Brayne, C., 2009. Prevalence, correlates and course of behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia in the population. *Br. J. Psychiatry* 194 (3), 212–219. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.108.049619>.
- Sayma, M., Tuijt, R., Cooper, C., Walters, K., 2020. Are we there yet? Immersive virtual reality to improve cognitive function in dementia and mild cognitive impairment. *Gerontologist* 60 (7), 502–512. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnz132>.
- Schiza, E., Matsangidou, M., Neokleous, K., Pattichis, C.S., 2019. Virtual reality applications for neurological disease: a review. *Front. Robot. AI* 6, 100.

- Schneider, C., Nißen, M., Kowatsch, T., Vinay, R., 2024. Impact of digital assistive technologies on the quality of life for people with dementia: a scoping review. *BMJ Open* 14 (2), e080545. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2023-080545>.
- Selbæk, G., Engedal, K., Bergh, S., 2013. The prevalence and course of neuropsychiatric symptoms in nursing home patients with dementia: a systematic review. *J. Am. Med. Dir. Assoc.* 14 (3), 161–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jamda.2012.09.027>.
- Shega, J.W., Hougham, G.W., Stocking, C.B., Cox-Hayley, D., Sachs, G.A., 2004. Pain in community-dwelling persons with dementia: frequency, intensity, and congruence between patient and caregiver report. *J. Pain Symptom Manag.* 28 (6), 585–592. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpainsymman.2004.04.012>.
- Shen, C., Rollis, E.T., Cheng, W., Kang, J., Dong, G., Xie, C., Zhao, X.M., Sahakian, B.J., Feng, J., 2022. Associations of social isolation and loneliness with later dementia. *Neurology* 99 (2), e164–e175. <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.000000000000200583>.
- Siriaraya, P., Ang, C.S., 2014. Recreating living experiences from past memories through virtual worlds for people with dementia. In: Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, pp. 3977–3986. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2556288.2557035>.
- Statista. 2024. Digital therapeutics worldwide. Retrieved October 1, 2024, from: <https://www.statista.com/outlook/hmo/digital-health/digital-treatment-care/digital-the-rapeutics/worldwide>.
- Sultana, M., Campbell, K., Jennings, M., Montero-Odasso, M., Orange, J.B., Knowlton, J., St George, A., Bryant, D., 2020. Virtual reality experience in long term care resident older adults with dementia: a case series. doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-16210/v3.
- Sultana, M., Campbell, K., Jennings, M., Montero-Odasso, M., Orange, J.B., Knowlton, J., St George, A., Bryant, D., 2021. Virtual reality experience intervention may reduce responsive behaviors in nursing home residents with dementia: a case series. *J. Alzheimer's Dis.* 84 (2), 883–893. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-210010>.
- Sutin, A.R., Stephan, Y., Luchetti, M., Terracciano, A., 2020. Loneliness and risk of dementia. *J. Gerontol. Ser. B* 75 (7), 1414–1422. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/gby112>.
- Ta, V., Griffith, C., Boatfield, C., Wang, X., Civitello, M., Bader, H., DeCero, E., Loggarakis, A., 2020. User experiences of social support from companion chatbots in everyday contexts: thematic analysis. *J. Med. Internet Res.* 22 (3), e16235. <https://doi.org/10.2196/16235>.
- Tabbaa, L., Ang, C.S., Rose, V., Siriaraya, P., Stewart, I., Jenkins, K.G., Matsangidou, M., 2019. Bring the outside in: providing accessible experiences through VR for people with dementia in locked psychiatric hospitals. In: Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, pp. 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300466>.
- Tariot, P.N., Mack, J.L., Patterson, M.B., Edland, S.D., Weiner, M.F., Fillenbaum, G., Blazina, L., Teri, L., Rubin, E., Mortimer, J.A., Stern, Y., Behavioral Pathology Committee of the Consortium to Establish a Registry for Alzheimer's Disease, 1995. The behavior rating scale for dementia of the consortium to establish a registry for Alzheimer's disease. *Psychopharmacol. Bull.* 31 (2), 1349–1357.
- Teno, J.M., Weitzen, S., Wetle, T., Mor, V., 2001. Persistent pain in nursing home residents. *JAMA* 285 (16), 2081. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.285.16.2081-a>.
- Teri, L., Truax, P., Logsdon, R., Uomoto, J., Zarit, S., Vitaliano, P.P., 1992. Assessment of behavioral problems in dementia: the revised memory and behavior problems checklist. *Psychol. Aging* 7 (4), 622–631. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0882-7974.7.4.622>.
- Thomas, J.M., Sezgin, D., 2021. Effectiveness of reminiscence therapy in reducing agitation and depression and improving quality of life and cognition in long-term care residents with dementia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Geriatr. Nurs.* 42 (6), 1497–1506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gerinurse.2021.10.014> (Minneapolis).
- Tominari, M., Uozumi, R., Becker, C., Kinoshita, A., 2021. Reminiscence therapy using virtual reality technology affects cognitive function and subjective well-being in older adults with dementia. *Cogent Psychol.* 8 (1), 1968991. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311908.2021.1968991>.
- Tractenberg, R.E., Weiner, M.F., Thal, L.J., 2002. Estimating the prevalence of agitation in community-dwelling persons with Alzheimer's disease. *J. Neuropsychiatry Clin. Neurosci.* 14 (1), 11–18.
- Valmaggia, L.R., Freeman, D., Green, C., Garety, P., Swapp, D., Antley, A., Prescott, C., et al., 2007. Virtual reality and paranoid ideations in people with an 'at-risk mental state' for psychosis. *Br. J. Psychiatry* 191 (S51), s63–s68. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.191.51.s63>.
- van t'Hof, C.E., Zwakhalen, S.M., Hamers, J.P., 2011. Interventions after diagnosing pain in nursing home residents with dementia: the pilot implementation of an observational pain scale (PACSLAC-D). *Tijdschr. Gerontol. Geriatr.* 42 (2), 67–78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12439-011-0012-7>.
- Verbeek, H., Zwakhalen, S.M., van Rossum, E., Ambergen, T., Kempen, G.I., Hamers, J.P., 2010. Dementia care redesigned: Effects of small-scale living facilities on residents, their family caregivers, and staff. *J. Am. Med. Dir. Assoc.* 11 (9), 662–670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jamda.2010.08.001>.
- Walden, A., Feliciano, L., 2022. A virtual reality intervention to reduce dementia-related agitation using single-case design. *Clin. Gerontol.* 45 (4), 1044–1054. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07317115.2021.1954121>.
- Waller, S., Masterson, A., 2015. Designing dementia-friendly hospital environments. *Future Hosp. J.* 2 (1), 63–68. <https://doi.org/10.7861/futurehosp.2-1-63>.
- Wang, Z., Li, Y., An, J., Dong, W., Li, H., Ma, H., Wang, J., Wu, J., Jiang, T., Wang, G., 2022. Effects of restorative environment and presence on anxiety and depression based on interactive virtual reality scenarios. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 19 (13), 7878. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19137878>.
- White, N., Leurent, B., Lord, K., Scott, S., Jones, L., Sampson, E.L., 2017. The management of behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia in the acute general medical hospital: a longitudinal cohort study. *Int. J. Geriatr. Psychiatry* 32 (3), 297–305. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gps.4463>.
- Wong, P.T., Watt, L.M., 1991. What types of reminiscence are associated with successful aging? *Psychol. Aging* 6 (2), 272–279. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0882-7974.6.2.272>.
- Wood, W., Womack, J., Hooper, B., 2009. Dying of boredom: An exploratory case study of time use, apparent affect, and routine activity situations on two Alzheimer's special care units. *Am. J. Occup. Ther.* 63 (3), 337–350. <https://doi.org/10.5014/ajot.63.3.337>.
- Woods, B., O'Philbin, L., Farrell, E.M., Spector, A.E., Orrell, M., 2018. Reminiscence therapy for dementia. *Cochrane Database Syst. Rev.* 3. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD001120.pub3>.
- World Health Organization (WHO). 2017. Global action plan on the public health response to dementia 2017–2025. Geneva: World Health Organization.
- World Health Organization (WHO). 2021. Dementia. Retrieved September 14, 2022, from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/dementia>.
- World Health Organization (WHO). International classification of diseases for mortality and morbidity statistics (11th Revision). Retrieved September 16, 2022, from <https://icd.who.int/>.
- Zakzanis, K.K., Quintin, G., Graham, S.J., Mraz, R., 2009. Age and dementia related differences in spatial navigation within an immersive virtual environment. *Med. Sci. Monit.* 15 (4), 140–150.
- Zeng, N., Pope, Z., Lee, J.E., Gao, Z., 2018. Virtual reality exercise for anxiety and depression: a preliminary review of current research in an emerging field. *J. Clin. Med.* 7 (3), 42–55. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm7030042>.
- Zhang, Y., Cai, J., An, Li, Hui, F., Ren, T., Ma, H., Zhao, Q., 2017. Does music therapy enhance behavioral and cognitive function in elderly dementia patients? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ageing Res. Rev.* 35, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arr.2016.12.003>.
- Zhu, S., Sui, Y., Shen, Y., Zhu, Yi, Ali, N., Guo, C., Wang, T., 2021. Effects of virtual reality intervention on cognition and motor function in older adults with mild cognitive impairment or dementia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front. Aging Neurosci.* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2021.586999>.
- Zuidema, S., Koopmans, R., Verhey, F., 2007. Prevalence and predictors of neuropsychiatric symptoms in cognitively impaired nursing home patients. *J. Geriatr. Psychiatry Neurol.* 20 (1), 41–49. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891988706292762>.